

**PANDUAN SUBMIT
JURNAL
BAGI PENULIS
JURNAL AL-MUAMALAT**

Opik Rozikin, SH., MH.

CIC Lembaga Riset dan
Konsultan Sosial)

Disampaikan pada

Pengembangan Jurusan

Hukum Ekonomi Syariah

UIN Sunan Gunung Djati

Bandung

REGISTER

1. Buka halaman <https://journal.uinsgd.ac.id/index.php/mua/index> melalui browser.

The screenshot shows the homepage of the journal 'Al-Muamalat'. The header features the journal title in large blue letters, with the subtitle 'Jurnal Hukum Ekonomi Syariah' in red below it. To the right, it lists the ISSN numbers (p-ISSN 2086 3225; e-ISSN 2716 0610), the journal's affiliation (PRODI HUKUM EKONOMI SYARIAH, Fakultas Syariah dan Hukum Universitas Islam Negeri Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung), and the address (Jl. Abdul Haris Nasution, No. 105 Bandung) along with the website URL. A navigation bar contains links for HOME, ABOUT, USER HOME, SEARCH, CURRENT, ARCHIVES, ANNOUNCEMENTS, EDITORIAL BOARD, and CONTACT. Below the navigation bar, the current issue is identified as 'Home > Vol 6, No 2 (2019)'. The main content area is titled 'Al-Muamalat' and includes a paragraph describing the journal's focus on Islamic economic development. A thumbnail image of the journal cover is displayed. On the right side, there is a sidebar with a button for 'OPEN JOURNAL SYSTEMS' and a list of 'ADDITIONAL MENU' items: EDITORIAL BOARD, FOCUS AND SCOPE, PEER-REVIEWERS, AUTHOR GUIDELINES, PUBLICATION ETHICS, ONLINE SUBMISSIONS, REGISTER, and OPEN ACCESS POLICY.

Al-Muamalat
Jurnal Hukum Ekonomi Syariah

p-ISSN 2086 3225; e-ISSN 2716 0610
PRODI HUKUM EKONOMI SYARIAH
Fakultas Syariah dan Hukum Universitas Islam Negeri
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<https://journal.uinsgd.ac.id/index.php/mua/index>

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Home > Vol 6, No 2 (2019)

Al-Muamalat

Al-Muamalat (P-ISSN : 2086-3225 E-ISSN: 2716-0610) adalah Jurnal pengembangan Ekonomi Syari'ah yang diterbitkan pertama kali oleh Jurusan Muamalah Fakultas Syari'ah dan Hukum UIN Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung. Terbit setiap enam bulan sekali sebagai media publikasi makalah ilmiah, sinopsis laporan penelitian dan pembahasan buku bidang Ekonomi Syari'ah. Isi atau artikel yang dimuat dalam Jurnal ini tidak mencerminkan pandangan dan pemikiran redaksi atau insititusi. Jurnal Al-Muamalat terbit dua setiap dua kali dalam satu tahun yaitu bulan Januari dan Juli.

OPEN JOURNAL SYSTEMS

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- EDITORIAL BOARD
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- PEER-REVIEWERS
- AUTHOR GUIDELINES
- PUBLICATION ETHICS
- ONLINE SUBMISSIONS
- REGISTER
- OPEN ACCESS POLICY

2. Klik link **REGISTER** pada jurnal yang akan dituju, sehingga muncul form regaister sebagai berikut:

Register

Fill in this form to register with this site.
[Click here](#) if you are already registered with this or another journal on this site.

Profile

Username *
The username must contain only lowercase letters, numbers, and hyphens/underscores.

Password *
The password must be at least 6 characters.

Repeat password *

Validation * I'm not a robot reCAPTCHA
Privacy - Terms

Salutation

First Name *

Middle Name

Last Name *

Initials Joan Alice Smith = JAS

Gender

Affiliation
(Your institution, e.g. "Simon Fraser University")

Signature

Email * [PRIVACY STATEMENT](#)

Confirm Email *

ORCID iD
ORCID iDs can only be assigned by [the ORCID Registry](#). You must conform to their standards for

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- EDITORIAL BOARD
- FOCUS AND SCOPE
- PEER-REVIEWERS
- AUTHOR GUIDELINES
- PUBLICATION ETHICS
- ONLINE SUBMISSIONS
- REGISTER**
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9 772086 522000

9 772718 081002

INFORMATION

- » For Readers
- » For Authors
- » For Librarians

KEYWORDS

- **Username**, diisi dengan nama yang akan digunakan untuk login
- **Password**, diisi dengan kata sandi yang unik dan mudah diingat minimal 6 karakter
- **Repeat password**, diisi dengan kata sandi yang sama
- **Validation**, masukkan kode validasi pada kotak isian yang disediakan
- **Salutation**, dapat diisi dengan Mr. atau Mrs.
- **First Name**, wajib diisi dengan nama depan
- **Middle Name**, dapat diisi dengan nama tengah
- **Last Name**, wajib diisi dengan nama belakang, jika namanya terdiri dari satu suku kata, last name dapat diisi dengan gelar atau suatu karakter, titik “.” misalnya.
- **Initials**, *dapat diisi dengan inisial nama*
- **Gender**, dapat dipilih sesuai dengan jenis kelamin, male atau female (lelaki atau perempuan)
- **Affiliation**, dapat diisi dengan institusi tempat bekerja atau menuntut ilmu.
- **Signature**, dapat diisi dengan tanda tangan elektronik.
- **Email**, wajib diisi dengan alamat email yang masih aktif
- **ORCID ID**, dapat diisi dengan nomor identitas digital peneliti jika ada.
- **URL**, dapat diisi dengan alamat profil google scholar atau alamat blog kita yang masih aktif.

Phone *

Fax

Mailing Address

Country

Bio Statement
(E.g., department and rank)

Confirmation

Send me a confirmation email including my username and password

Working Languages

Bahasa Indonesia

English

Register as

Reader: Notified by email on publication of an issue of the journal.

Author: Able to submit items to the journal.

Reviewer: Willing to conduct peer review of submissions to the site.

Identify reviewing interests (substantive areas and research methods):

Register

Cancel

* Denotes required field

Privacy Statement

The names and email addresses entered in this journal site will be used exclusively for the stated purposes of this journal and will not be made available for any other purpose or to any other party.

Creditor Debitor E-Money Ekonomi syariah, asuransi kesehatan, BPJS Electronic money, E-Toll, al-Hurriyyah principle Hukum Ekonomi Syariah, jual beli buku bajakan, Toko Buku Kairo Insurance Kafalah Letter of Credit, Fatwa Dewan Syariah Nasional, Akad

Murabahah Ujrah. Wakalah

multilateral financing people's business

credit ujrah wakalah wakalah bil ujrah

contract . حماية المستهلك . ضمان عمر ناروير .
الشريعة الاقتصادية

- **Phone**, diisi dengan no telepon yang dapat dihubungi
- **Fax**, diisi dengan no fax yang dapat dihubungi
- **Mailing Address**, diisi dengan alamat surat menyurat.
- **Country**, diisi dengan nama Negara sesuai dengan kewarganegaraan.
- **Bio statement**, dapat diisi dengan biodata ringkas
- **Confirmation**, opsi agar sistem mengirimkan Username dan Password ke email.
- **Working languages**, kita dapat menentukan bahasa yang digunakan oleh sistem pada interface aplikasi OJS.
- **Register as**, secara default hanya **Reader** atau pembaca yang terchecklist, agar dapat mengirimkan artikel dapat memberikan check list juga pada bagian **Author**, atau Check list bagian **Reviewer** jika ingin mengajukan diri sebagai reviewer.
- Semua isian yang mengandung tanda asterik atau bintang "*" itu wajib diisi, yang lainnya dapat diisi sesuai kebutuhan.
- Selanjutnya klik tombol REGISTER untuk mendaftar.

3. Muncul gambar berikut

[HOME](#) | [ABOUT](#) | [USER HOME](#) | [SEARCH](#) | [CURRENT](#) | [ARCHIVES](#) | [ANNOUNCEMENTS](#) | [EDITORIAL BOARD](#) | [CONTACT](#)

Home > [User Home](#)

User Home

Al-Muamalat

Journal Manager

[\[Setup\]](#)

Editor

1 Unassigned 0 In Review 0 In Editing

[\[Create Issue\]](#) [\[Notify Users\]](#)

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[ONLINE SUBMISSIONS](#)

[REGISTER](#)

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[Journal Help](#)

[NOTIFICATIONS](#)

SUBMIT ARTIKEL

- Untuk dapat mengirimkan artikel jurnal, peran user-nya harus sebagai Author pada jurnal tersebut, jika tidak maka tidak akan dapat mengirimkan artikel jurnal tersebut. Berikut langkah-langkah yang dilakukan untuk mengirimkan artikel jurnal:
- Login di halaman login atau di block login yang tersedia di halaman depan website jurnal

Al-Muamalat

Jurnal Hukum Ekonomi Syariah

p-ISSN 2086 3225; e-ISSN 2716 0610

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[HOME](#) [ABOUT](#) [LOGIN](#) [REGISTER](#) [SEARCH](#) [CURRENT](#) [ARCHIVES](#) [ANNOUNCEMENTS](#) [EDITORIAL BOARD](#) [CONTACT](#)

Home > [Login](#)

Login

Username

Password

Remember my username and password

- [Not a user? Register with this site](#)
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[PUBLICATION ETHICS](#)

[ONLINE SUBMISSIONS](#)

[REGISTER](#)

[OPEN ACCESS POLICY](#)

[Journal Help](#)

[NOTIFICATIONS](#)

2. Setelah login, maka masuk ke halaman dashboard author seperti pada gambar berikut:

The screenshot displays the author dashboard for the journal 'Al-Muamalat'. The header features the journal's title in large blue letters, its subtitle 'Jurnal Hukum Ekonomi Syariah' in red, and contact information including p-ISSN 2086 3225, e-ISSN 2716 0610, and the address of the Faculty of Sharia and Law at UIN Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung. A navigation bar below the header contains links for HOME, ABOUT, USER HOME, SEARCH, CURRENT, ARCHIVES, ANNOUNCEMENTS, EDITORIAL BOARD, and CONTACT. The main content area is titled 'User Home' and shows the user's role as 'Journal Manager' with a '[Setup]' link. Below this, a status bar indicates '1 Unassigned', '0 In Review', and '0 In Editing' articles, along with '[Create Issue]' and '[Notify Users]' buttons. A 'My Account' section provides links for 'Show My Journals', 'Edit My Profile', 'Change My Password', and 'Logout'. A Google search bar is located at the bottom left. On the right side, a sidebar contains a 'Journal Help' button and a 'NOTIFICATIONS' section.

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Home > **User Home**

User Home

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Journal Manager [Setup]
Editor 1 Unassigned 0 In Review 0 In Editing [Create Issue] [Notify Users]

My Account

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- Edit My Profile
- Change My Password
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- EDITORIAL BOARD
- FOCUS AND SCOPE
- PEER-REVIEWERS
- AUTHOR GUIDELINES
- PUBLICATION ETHICS
- ONLINE SUBMISSIONS
- REGISTER
- OPEN ACCESS POLICY

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NOTIFICATIONS

3. Selanjutnya, klik **new submission**, ada lima langkah yang harus dilalui agar artikel yang dikirim dapat diproses dalam OJS.

Step 1. Starting the Submission

1. **START** 2. **UPLOAD SUBMISSION** 3. **ENTER METADATA** 4. **UPLOAD SUPPLEMENTARY FILES** 5. **CONFIRMATION**

Encountering difficulties? Contact Opik Rozikin for assistance (085862536992).

Submission Checklist

Indicate that this submission is ready to be considered by this journal by checking off the following (comments to the editor can be added below).

- The submission has not been previously published, nor is it before another journal for consideration (or an explanation has been provided in Comments to the Editor).
- The submission file is in OpenOffice, Microsoft Word, RTF, or WordPerfect document file format.
- Where available, URLs for the references have been provided.
- The text is single-spaced; uses a 12-point font; employs italics, rather than underlining (except with URL addresses); and all illustrations, figures, and tables are placed within the text at the appropriate points, rather than at the end.
- The text adheres to the stylistic and bibliographic requirements outlined in the Author Guidelines, which is found in About the Journal.
- If submitting to a peer-reviewed section of the journal, the instructions in Ensuring a Blind Review have been followed.

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4. Pada langkah pertama **Starting The Submission**, pastikan artikel yang akan diunggah sudah memenuhi persyaratan **Submission Checklist** yang telah ditentukan oleh pengelola jurnal masing-masing. jika artikelnya sudah memenuhi persyaratan dan ketentuan yang diminta, beri tanda checklist pada semua Submission Checklist.

Step 1. Starting the Submission

1. START 2. UPLOAD SUBMISSION 3. ENTER METADATA 4. UPLOAD SUPPLEMENTARY FILES 5. CONFIRMATION

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5. Selanjutnya, perhatikan terkait pemberitahuan hak cipta, tiap jurnal akan memiliki kebijakan yang berbeda terkait hak cipta. Beri tanda centang jika setuju dengan ketentuan (V).

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If the article was jointly prepared by other authors, any authors submitting the manuscript warrants that he/she has been authorized by all co-authors to be agreed on this copyright and license notice (agreement) on their behalf, and agrees to inform his/her co-authors of the terms of this policy. 'ADLIYA : Jurnal Hukum dan Kemanusiaan will not be held liable for anything that may arise due to the author(s) internal dispute. 'ADLIYA : Jurnal Hukum dan Kemanusiaan will only communicate with the corresponding author.

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The authors agree to the terms of this Copyright Notice, which will apply to this submission if and when it is published by this journal (comments to the editor can be added below).

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Comments for the Editor

Enter text (optional)

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ISSN (Online) Barcode

FONT SIZE

INFORMATION

- » For Readers
- » For Authors
- » For Librarians

KEYWORDS

Ahli hukum, agdi, Recall, dan Partai Politik, Bank OCB, NISP, Sjarah, Budaya, Organisasi, Cerai talak, mutah, narkah, iddah, narkah anak, Hukum Islam, Islamic Economics, Industrial Revolution 4.0, and

6. Jika ada komentar untuk editor, dapat diisikan pada kotak isian **Comments For The Editor**, dan selanjutnya klik tombol **Save And Continue**.

7. Langkah selanjutnya yaitu **Uploading The Submission**, klik tombol **Pilih File/Choose File** dan arahkan ke direktori dimana file artikel berada dan kemudian klik **Upload** atau **Unggah**. Dan klik **Save And Continue** untuk

Home > User > Author > Submissions > New Submission

Step 2. Uploading the Submission

1. START 2. **UPLOAD SUBMISSION** 3. ENTER METADATA 4. UPLOAD SUPPLEMENTARY FILES 5. CONFIRMATION

To upload a manuscript to this journal, complete the following steps.

1. On this page, click Browse (or Choose File) which opens a Choose File window for locating the file on the hard drive of your computer.
2. Locate the file you wish to submit and highlight it.
3. Click Open on the Choose File window, which places the name of the file on this page.
4. Click Upload on this page, which uploads the file from the computer to the journal's web site and renames it following the journal's conventions.
5. Once the submission is uploaded, click Save and Continue at the bottom of this page.

Encountering difficulties? Contact [Opik Rozikin](#) for assistance (085862536992).

Submission File

File Name 10214-29492-1-SM.pdf
Original file name TUTORIAL SUBMIT JURNAL.pdf
File Size 1MB
Date uploaded 2020-11-16 12:04 PM

Replace submission file

No file chosen

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ADDITIONAL MENU

EDITORIAL BOARD

FOCUS AND SCOPE

PEER-REVIEWERS

AUTHOR GUIDELINES

PUBLICATION ETHICS

ONLINE SUBMISSIONS

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8. Langkah berikutnya adalah **entering the submission's metadata** di sini penulis diminta untuk melengkapi metadata atau informasi yang terkait dengan artikel yang di upload, yaitu informasi penulis, Jika penulis lebih dari satu, dapat ditambahkan penulis lainnya dengan cara mengklik tombol **Add Author**

HOME ABOUT USER HOME SEARCH CURRENT ARCHIVES ANNOUNCEMENTS EDITORIAL BOARD CONTACT

Home > User > Author > Submissions > **New Submission**

Step 3. Entering the Submission's Metadata

1. START 2. UPLOAD SUBMISSION **3. ENTER METADATA** 4. UPLOAD SUPPLEMENTARY FILES 5. CONFIRMATION

Authors

First Name *

Middle Name

Last Name *

Email *

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URL

Affiliation
(Your institution, e.g. "Simon Fraser University")

Country

Bio Statement (E.g., department and rank)

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- EDITORIAL BOARD
- FOCUS AND SCOPE
- PEER-REVIEWERS
- AUTHOR GUIDELINES
- PUBLICATION ETHICS
- ONLINE SUBMISSIONS
- REGISTER
- OPEN ACCESS POLICY

Journal Help

NOTIFICATIONS

- » View (46 new)
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INFORMATION

9. Kemudian selain informasi penulis, dalam metadata juga diminta informasi tentang judul artikel, abstract, kata kunci, bahasa yang digunakan dan referensi dari artikel yang ditulis.

Title and Abstract

Title *

Abstract *

» For Readers
» For Authors
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KEYWORDS

Akad tabarru BSM E-Money Bad Debts
Creditor Debitor E-Money Ekonomi syariah,
asuransi kesehatan, BPJS Electronic money,
E-Toll, al-Humiyah principle Hukum
Ekonomi Syariah, jual beli buku bajakan,
Toko Buku Kairo Insurance Kafalah Letter of
Credit, Fatwa Dewan Syariah Nasional, Akad
Murabahah Ujrah. **Wakalah**
multilateral financing people's business
credit ujrah wakalah wakalah bil ujrah
contract - ضمان عمر تايؤر - ضمانة المستهلك -
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Indexing

Provide terms for indexing the submission; separate terms with a semi-colon (term1; term2; term3).

Keywords

Language

English=en; French=fr; Spanish=es. [Additional codes.](#)

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Identify agencies (a person, an organization, or a service) that made contributions to the content or provided funding or support for the work presented in this submission. Separate them with a semi-colon (e.g. John Doe, Metro University; Master University, Department of Computer Science).

Agencies

References

Provide a formatted list of references for works cited in this submission. Please separate individual references with a blank line.

References

10. Pada langkah berikutnya, **UPLOADING SUPPLEMENTARY FILES**, Penulis dapat menambahkan file tambahan seperti instrumen penelitian atau gambar/tabel yang belum tercantum dalam artikel yang telah diunggah. Klik **Pilih File/Choose File** untuk mencari file tambahan yang akan diunggah dan klik **Upload** untuk mengunggah file tambahan. Selanjutnya klik **Save and Continue** untuk melanjutkan ke langkah berikutnya

Step 4. Uploading Supplementary Files

1. START 2. UPLOAD SUBMISSION 3. ENTER METADATA 4. **UPLOAD SUPPLEMENTARY FILES** 5. CONFIRMATION

This optional step allows Supplementary Files to be added to a submission. The files, which can be in any format, might include (a) research instruments, (b) data sets, which comply with the terms of the study's research ethics review, (c) sources that otherwise would be unavailable to readers, (d) figures and tables that cannot be integrated into the text itself, or other materials that add to the contribution of the work.

ID	TITLE	ORIGINAL FILE NAME	DATE UPLOADED	ACTION
<i>No supplementary files have been added to this submission.</i>				
Upload supplementary file		<input type="text"/>	<input type="button" value="Browse..."/>	<input type="button" value="Upload"/>
<input type="button" value="Save and continue"/>		<input type="button" value="Cancel"/>		

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- PUBLICATION ETHICS
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Activate Window
Go to Settings to activate

11. Dan langkah terakhir **Confirming The Submission**, untuk mengkonfirmasi pengiriman artikel

Step 5. Confirming the Submission

1. START 2. UPLOAD SUBMISSION 3. ENTER METADATA 4. UPLOAD SUPPLEMENTARY FILES 5. **CONFIRMATION**

To submit your manuscript to ADLIYA: Jurnal Hukum dan Kemanusiaan click Finish Submission. The submission's principal contact will receive an acknowledgement by email and will be able to view the submission's progress through the editorial process by logging in to the journal web site. Thank you for your interest in publishing with ADLIYA: Jurnal Hukum dan Kemanusiaan.

File Summary

ID	ORIGINAL FILE NAME	TYPE	FILE SIZE	DATE UPLOADED
16724	TOR PELATIHAN KTI.DOC	Submission File	272KB	10-06

Finish Submission

Cancel

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12. Pada tahap terakhir, tampak file yang telah diunggah beserta informasi ID artikel, ukuran file dan tanggal file yang diunggah. Untuk mengakhiri proses pengiriman artikel klik tombol **Finish Submission**. Selanjutnya tampak seperti berikut:

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- Active Submissions

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